

IIB: COMPUTATIONAL HUMOR-BASED CHANGE AGENT

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HOW TO USE IIB: GENERAL INSTRUCTION (v. 1.0)

IIB is a blind, humor-based computational change agent, which is made for emergence of flat, non-hierarchical experimental collaboration forms of professionals, who can behave as individuals, authors of collaborations, and their members. By applying humor, IIB shows to the users, if they have honestly graded the jokes, how they naturally perceive clashes and fracture under uncertainty, common in the processes of change and sudden hair-raising transformation events, when experimenting is the way to change the status-quo and achieve. Also, when the users are clustered in collaborations, IIB shows them a diversity of their qualities and needs as a group in situations of fracture, clash, experiment, and high uncertainty. IIB disrupts comfort zones and conventional ways of decision making by providing challenge, ease, and support.

FOR INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONALS

As an independent professional, you may be anybody: curious self-sustainable doer with a broad knowledge horizon, specialist, operative worker, leader, freelancer, nerd, creator, misfit, intuitive introvert, or the one wishing changes but afraid to look stupid, or you may be involved in parallel projects and willing to get support or be willing to challenge yourself regularly.

You create your user by going through "Begin as an independent professional". A specified instruction about this precedes that process. When your user is created, you may be passively available in the system to get contacted by the collaborations that would need your qualities. Or, you may begin your own collaborations by using the blind functionalities of IIB which shall find for you other independent professionals, being helpful and constructively challenged to collaborate with you, if available to get involved into the experimental processes that you would wish to start despite the uncertainty on your way to your goals. Also, you may invite someone you know. In both situations you create your own collaborations to (re-)structure and lead.

FOR AUTHORS OF COLLABORATIONS

As an author of a collaboration, you are an independent professional (see above), but you have a clear intention to experiment when you experience uncertainty in your collective: to get a holistic picture of its intellectual needs and competencies in change, increase hybridization of knowledge, disrupt its comfort zones in a way that nothing would collapse, build parallel collaborative processes, each of which being experimental, and bring in new blood.

You create your user by going through “Begin as an author of a collaboration”. A specified instruction about this precedes. First, you select a set of knowledge areas that characterize the collaboration you are starting. You can change them later. Then, you enjoy the jokes and select your own knowledge spheres. When your user is created, you will see your own intellectual and immaterial capital in the context of fracture and change, and you will be asked to add members into your collaboration, because a collaboration consists of two and more professionals. You will be provided with the options how to do that: either by blind computation of IIB or by manual invitations. Your collaboration may be passively available in the IIB computational system to get contacted by any new, unknown to you independent professionals, who are helpful and wish to be challenged. Actively, you can search for any new independent professionals on your own: from the entire IIB population, “externally”, or from any of your previous endeavors and their endeavors, “internally”, provided those professionals happen to be in the system as its users.

FOR BOTH

IIB is blind. Introduce yourself when you have found interesting independent professionals or collaborations. Even if they happen to know you, they will not know you in the IIB system until you introduce yourself. Be creative and brief, but concrete and honest, when you wish to involve or join. IIB has already considered much, including imagination, to propose you those whom you see on your screen, and they are brought to you with some surprises, based on your results. Moreover, both sides, being compatible by a set of surprises, including that in the long run, are encouraged to learn new knowledge areas mutually, on having the collaboration established.

If available for collaboration, any professional can be reached. It can be someone completely new to the requesting side: that happens when the requesting side chooses to look “externally”. There can also be found somebody already known from before, that is from any previous endeavors of the requesting side back in the past, by a certain set of surprises. If this is the case, you might meet your former colleagues, for example. You may see them in a new, unexpected light, and discover in them some new capacities, which you previously overlooked: that happens when the requesting side chooses to look “internally”. The “previous endeavors” are created by the independent professionals directly, entirely bottom up, when they choose to invite into their collaborations someone that they know, manually, bypass the blind options.

You have several options to (re-)structure and lead your collaborations, which you can have as many as you need, for different purposes. You can manage your data and settings. You own your data, which you can delete at any time, including your collaborations. On the right side of the screen, you see the options for taking actions; on the left, the menu of what you have done.

By creating a user, you confirm that you act on a good will, and you will not use the IIB system to cause any harm to any persons, collaborations, organizations, and any other individual and collective actors of professionals. By using the IIB system, you will not take any actions in breach of any legal agreements you are obliged to keep. You agree to be a person of integrity. The use of IIB shall lead to hybridization of knowledge for lifelong learning, and to novel, dynamic, creative, peaceful, and flat collaborative processes of their members and authors.